

MICROMECHANICS STUDY OF THE PROPAGATION
RATE OF A STRESS CORROSION CRACK IN CROSS PLY GLASS/EPOXY
LAMINATES UNDER ACID ENVIRONMENTS

Hideki Sekine

Department of Engineering Science, Tohoku University,
Aramaki Aza Aoba, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980, Japan

ABSTRACT

The propagation rate of a stress corrosion crack in cross ply glass/epoxy laminates exposed to acid environments is considered. Stress corrosion crack tests were carried out on compact tension specimens of a cross ply E-glass/epoxy laminate in 0.5N HCl. Then, it has been verified that the crack propagation rate da/dt is approximately expressed against the stress intensity factor K at crack tip in the form $da/dt = AK^m$ where A and m are constants. Next, this relationship has been examined from the viewpoint of micromechanics and is derived theoretically.

KEYWORDS: Crack Propagation; Micromechanics; Glass/Epoxy Laminate; Stress Corrosion Crack; Environmental Effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

As a result of the increasing use of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) as structural components in corrosive environments, the study of the combined influence of stresses and corrosive environments has received wide attention. As for the propagation of stress corrosion cracks in GFRP, some investigators has studied so far (for example, Aveston and Sillwood[1], Price and Hull[2,3] and Hsu, Yau and Chou[4]). On the basis of linear elastic fracture mechanics, they have presented an empirical relationship between the crack propagation rate da/dt and the stress intensity factor K at the crack tip, which is expressed in the form $da/dt = AK^m$ where A and m are experimental constants. However, few works of the theoretical examination of this relationship have been done.

In this paper, stress corrosion crack tests were carried out on compact tension specimens of a cross ply E-glass/epoxy laminate in 0.5N HCl under constant loading. The crack propagation rate was plotted against the

stress intensity factor at crack tip. Then, it has been verified that the relationship $da/dt = AK^m$ is approximately valid. In the next place, the micromechanics study has been made on this relationship.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material The material is a glass/epoxy laminate which contains continuous E-glass fibers of $13\mu\text{m}$ diameter in an epoxy resin matrix. The laminate was fabricated from forty four prepregged layers with stacking sequence $(0/90/\dots/0/90)_S$. The final thickness of the laminate was 6mm. The fiber volume fraction was 52.4%.

The compact tension specimens used in stress corrosion crack tests were machined from the laminate with side grooves, as shown in Figure 1. At the bottom of the grooves, they were 1.6mm thick and the layup was $(0/90/0/90/0/90)_S$.

The fracture toughness value K_Q of the laminate in air, which is obtained by the 5% offset procedure[5] is $18.2 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$.

2.2 Experimental Procedure Stress corrosion crack tests were carried out in 0.5N HCl at 298K under constant loading, as illustrated in Figure 2. The load was applied to the specimens by use of a weight of 14kg. During the tests, the crack mouth displacements of the specimens were measured at intervals by a linear variable displacement transducer (Shinko Denshi; MH-500D, AC-1P4209).

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The stress corrosion crack has propagated from the notch tip and is essentially planar. The crack propagation length is evaluated from the crack mouth displacement measurements by means of a finite element method, and the crack propagation rate is obtained as the derivative of the crack propagation length with respect to time. Figure 3 shows the crack propagation rate da/dt against the stress intensity factor K at the crack tip. The data of the crack propagation rate are obtained from the average values over the interval of 4~24 hours. It can be found from the figure that $\log(da/dt)$ shows a general tendency to increase almost linearly with $\log K$, as indicated by the broken line. That is, the crack propagation rate da/dt is approximately expressed against the stress intensity factor K in the form $da/dt = AK^m$ where $A = 6.9 \times 10^{-11}$ and $m = 3.6$.

4. MICROMECHANICS APPROACH

4.1 Model of Propagation Mechanism of Stress Corrosion Crack When the stress corrosion crack propagates macroscopically, the glass fibers in the 0° -plies are broken one by one successively. The crack propagation is

shown schematically in Figure 4.

Figure 5 shows the model of fracture mechanism of the glass fiber[6,7]. The stress corrosion crack initiates at a preexisting microcrack on the surface of the glass fiber. After that, the crack propagates perpendicular to the fiber direction with time by stress corrosion. In the end, the brittle fracture of the glass fiber occurs and the crack propagates into the surrounding matrix.

4.2 Evaluation of Crack Propagation Rate Assume that the shape of the front of the stress corrosion crack in the glass fibers is a circular arc with a constant radius r_0 , which is the radius of the fibers, as shown in Figure 6. Then, the reaction equation of glass to HCl at the crack front in the glass fibers is expressed in the form[8]

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = - 2nr_0\theta k_{S_0} C_E \exp\left(\frac{\alpha K_I}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where X the area of nonreacting part of glass fiber on the plane including the stress corrosion crack, t time, n the molar ratio of glass to HCl, θ the half angle made by two radii of the glass fiber, which encloses the stress corrosion crack, k_{S_0} is the reaction rate constant of glass to HCl, C_E the concentration of HCl, α an experimental constant, K_I the stress intensity factor of mode I at the crack front in the glass fiber, R the gas constant and T absolute temperature. On the other hand, geometrical consideration of the area of the stress corrosion crack gives

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = - \frac{dY}{dt} = - 4r_0^2 \sin^2\theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where Y is the area of the stress corrosion crack in the glass fiber. From Eqs. (1) and (2), we obtain

$$dt = \frac{2r_0}{nk_{S_0} C_E} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\theta} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha K_I}{RT}\right) d\theta \quad (3)$$

By performing the integration, the time required during the stress corrosion cracking of a glass fiber, t_f , is given by

$$t_f = \frac{2r_0}{nk_{S_0} C_E} \int_{\theta_0}^{\theta_f} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\theta} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha K_I}{RT}\right) d\theta \quad (4)$$

where θ_0 is the half angle made by two radii of the glass fiber, which encloses the preexisting microcrack and θ_f is the half angle at the breakage of the glass fiber.

When the front of the stress corrosion crack in the glass fiber under a tensile stress is a circular arc with the radius r_0 , the stress intensity

factor K_I is almost constant along the crack front and is approximately written as

$$K_I = \sigma F(\theta) \sqrt{2\pi r_0} \quad (5)$$

where σ is the tensile stress applied on the glass fiber and $F(\theta)$ is expressed in the form

$$F(\theta) = \sqrt{1 - \cos\theta} \{1.12 - 2.57(1 - \cos\theta) + 13.87(1 - \cos\theta)^2 - 14.37(1 - \cos\theta)^3\} \quad (6)$$

When the brittle fracture of the glass fiber occurs, we obtain

$$K_{IC(g)} = \sigma F(\theta_f) \sqrt{2\pi r_0} \quad (7)$$

where $K_{IC(g)}$ is the fracture toughness of the glass fiber.

Consider the relationship between the tensile stress σ and the stress intensity factor of mode I, K , at the tip of the macroscopic stress corrosion crack in the laminates. When the continuous glass fibers in each ply is supposed to be distributed in a doubly periodic square array, we obtain the distance between the neighboring fibers in the form

$$D_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{V_f}} r_0 \quad (8)$$

where V_f is the fiber volume fraction. Now, calculate the normal force N acting on the rectangular with the thickness of the laminate B and the length D_0 just ahead of the tip (Figure 7). Then, the normal force N is given by

$$N = B \int_0^{D_0} \frac{K}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} dr = KB \sqrt{\frac{2D_0}{\pi}} \quad (9)$$

Ahead of the tip, the load is mainly supported by the 0° -fibers. Therefore, the normal force N is also written as

$$N = \frac{\pi r_0^2 \sigma B V_0}{D_0} \quad (10)$$

where V_0 is the volume fraction of 0° -plies. From Eqs. (9) and (10), and by use of Eq. (8), we obtain the relationship between the tensile stress σ and the stress intensity factor K , as follows :

$$\sigma = \beta K \quad (11)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{1}{V_0 V_f} \sqrt{\frac{2V_f^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\pi^{\frac{3}{2}} r_0}} \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eq. (11) into Eq. (7), we get

$$\theta_f = F^{-1}\left(\frac{K_{IC}(g)}{\beta K \sqrt{2\pi r_0}}\right) \quad (13)$$

where F^{-1} is the inverse function of F .

Consequently, by substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) and using Eq. (11), the time t_f is expressed as

$$t_f = \frac{2r_0}{nk_{S_0}C_E} \int_{\theta_0}^{\theta_f} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\theta} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha\beta KF(\theta)\sqrt{2\pi r_0}}{RT}\right) d\theta \quad (14)$$

Since the time required to the brittle fractures of the glass fibers and the matrix is extremely shorter than the time t_f , the crack propagation rate da/dt is approximately given by

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{D_0}{t_f} \quad (15)$$

Substituting Eq. (14) into Eq. (15), we finally obtain the crack propagation rate da/dt as the function of the stress intensity factor K in the form

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{nk_{S_0}C_E D_0}{2r_0 \int_{\theta_0}^{\theta_f} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\theta} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha\beta KF(\theta)\sqrt{2\pi r_0}}{RT}\right) d\theta} \quad (16)$$

Now, let us introduce the following quantities

$$\xi = \frac{nk_{S_0}C_E D_0}{2r_0}, \quad \zeta = \frac{K_{IC}(g)}{\beta\sqrt{2\pi r_0}}, \quad \eta = \frac{\alpha K_{IC}(g)}{RT} \quad (17)$$

Then, Eq. (16) is rewritten as

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{\xi}{\int_{\theta_0}^{F^{-1}\{1/(K/\zeta)\}} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\theta} \exp\{-\eta(K/\zeta)F(\theta)\} d\theta} \quad (18)$$

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When the values of θ_0 , ξ , ζ and η are set, the crack propagation rate da/dt can be calculated from Eq. (18) for the stress intensity factor K . In view of the values that $\theta_0 < 2.5^\circ$ [7,9], $r_0 = 13\mu\text{m}$, $V_0 = 0.5$, $V_f = 0.524$, $\alpha = 0.106 \sim 0.222 \text{ m}^{\frac{5}{2}}/\text{mol}$ [10], $K_{IC}(g) = 0.77 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $T = 298\text{K}$ and $R = 8.31 \text{ J/mol}\cdot\text{K}$, we set the values of θ_0 , ξ , ζ and η as $\theta_0 = 0.215$, $\xi = 5.01 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m/s}$, $\zeta = 0.158 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $\eta = 36.0$. The calculated results of the crack propagation rate are shown against the stress intensity factor K by the solid line in Figure 3. It is found that the solid line agrees almost well with the broken line. That is, the complete explanation of the relationship ex-

pressed as $da/dt = AK^m$ has been presented from the viewpoint of the micro-mechanics study.

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REFERENCES

1. J. Aveston and J. M. Sillwood, J. Mater. Sci., 17, 3491 (1982).
2. J. N. Price and D. Hull, J. Mater. Sci., 18, 2798 (1983).
3. J. N. Price and D. Hull, Comp. Sci. Technol., 28, 193 (1987).
4. P. L. Hsu, S. S. Yau and T. W. Chou, J. Mater. Sci., 21, 3703 (1986).
5. E399-81, Annual Book of ASTM Standards, Part 10, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1982, P.592.
6. H. Sekine, H. Suzuki, T. Miyanaga and J. H. Chen, Proceedings of the KSME/JSME Joint Conference, Fracture and Strength '90, KSME/JSME, 1990, pp.194-199.
7. H. Sekine and T. Miyanaga, J. Mater. Sci., Japan, 39, 1545 (1990).
8. T. Miyanaga and H. Sekine, J. Mater. Sci., Japan, 39, 737 (1990).
9. G. M. Bartenev, Int. J. Fract. Mech., 5, 179 (1969).
10. S. M. Wiederhorn and L. H. Bolz, J. Am. Ceram. Soc., 53, 543 (1970).

Biography Hideki Sekine received his Doctor of Engineering degree in 1977 from Tohoku University. He has been a Professor of Engineering Science at Tohoku University since 1987. He teaches courses on introduction to mechanical engineering, fracture mechanics, mechanics of composites. His major research interests include micromechanics of composites, biomechanics of bones and theoretical study of geothermal energy, and he has published over 110 scientific papers. He received the MMIJ Prize in 1985.

FIGURE 1. Geometry of compact tension specimen

FIGURE 2. Schematic illustration of the equipment for stress corrosion crack tests

FIGURE 3. Crack propagation rate against the stress intensity factor at crack tip

FIGURE 4. Propagation of stress corrosion crack

FIGURE 5. Model of fracture mechanism of glass fibers

FIGURE 6. Shape of stress corrosion crack in glass fibers

FIGURE 7. Stress distribution ahead of the tip of macroscopic stress corrosion crack